

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR STUDENTS OF AGRICULTURAL SPECIALTY

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Abstract:

The article is the result of practical experience in using demonstration methods of teaching a foreign language where some methods of using informational communicative technologies are shown. The purpose of this article is to review the currently existing innovative pedagogical technologies and substantiate the feasibility of their practical application in the process of foreign languages teaching. The article discusses the currently existing innovative teaching technologies (Internet, software, hardware, slide presentations), the possibilities and advantages of their use in the process of foreign languages teaching, which highlights interest from the audience, increases the motivation for studying the foreign languages while this creates a special motivation.

Key Words: innovative teaching technologies, the Internet, software, hardware, slide presentations, computer technologists, game technologists, design skills

Introduction:

Interactive learning is a specific form of organization of cognitive activity, which has the goal of creating comfortable learning conditions in which each student feels comfortable and confident, considers himself successful and intelligent, increases self-confidence well enough as well. The essence of interactive learning is that the learning process takes place subject to the constant, active positive interaction of all students. When the teacher and student are equal. As a result of the organization of educational activities under such conditions, an atmosphere of interaction and cooperation is created in the classroom, which enables the teacher to become a real leader.

Interactive learning technologies are the organization of the learning process in which it is impossible for a student not to participate in the collective process of cognition. Each student has a specific task for which he/she must publicly report while the quality of the task assigned to the group may depend on his activities. Interactive teaching technologies provide for the planned result, separate interactive techniques that stimulate the process, high elevated interest, and activate mental capabilities.

Innovative forms of education, in general, can be divided into two groups: innovative forms of instruction based on Internet technologies and computer technologies. In turn, innovative forms of training based on Internet technologies can be synchronous and asynchronous. Synchronous ones include video conferencing, chats, providing real-time communication. Through an inexpensive Skype program, for example, online conferences and telephone conversations are widely held. This technology is easy to use, does not require additional time and financial costs for training, as it has already firmly entered the everyday life of every person. The only requirement is appropriate technical capabilities. Asynchronous forms include the use of technologies such as email, blog development, where communication can occur with a time interval. Creating a virtual space combines both synchronous and asynchronous forms of learning. This technology makes it possible to live in 3D format, whereby special content is developed and virtual interaction is carried out, the forms of which can be different: debates, role-playing games, exhibitions, presentations. The Internet is a rich storehouse of authentic, up-to-date material (texts, audio, video, etc.) and information, as well as means and opportunities for communication and building platforms that allow the exchange of ideas, opinions, and achievements. Moreover, we must not forget about the importance of the relevance of information. The publication of manuals sometimes takes years, information, vocabulary become obsolete, which negatively affects the validity of the courses taught, their correspondence to objective reality. According to studies, courses based on Internet materials are more successful, as they include up-to-date information and topics that are more meaningful, interesting and, therefore, more motivating.

Intelligent educational technology involves the integration of the most effective educational technologies in a holistic system. They cover various algorithms of interaction between teachers and students with the active use of modern technical means in the educational process. IOT suggest:

- multifaceted cooperation and personal contacts of the teacher and students;
- increasing the effectiveness of individual educational and creative activities of students;
- mandatory communication of scientific and educational research of students with the content of the educational process;

- increase in the volume of independent work of students;
- close connection of theory and practice;
- controllability and continuous possibility of correction of the learning process, etc.

The main feature and distinctive feature of student training at innovative universities is the focus on the training of scientific personnel capable of developing university scientific potential, as well as on meeting the needs of the high-tech sector of the economy. In the framework of innovative educational projects of leading universities, programs are being implemented for the active use of intellectual educational technologies, which imply the obligatory relationship between the educational, scientific and practical tasks, and the multifaceted cooperation between teachers and students. With such a target setting, cognitive universal actions are one of the leading components of the educational standard. In this regard, cognitive universal actions include:

- actions to extract information;
- the ability to navigate the knowledge system and recognize the need for new knowledge;
- the ability to pre-select sources of information to search for new knowledge.

Currently, innovative teaching technologies (Internet, software, hardware, slide presentations), the possibilities and advantages of their use in the process of teaching foreign languages, which arouse interest in the audience, increase the motivation for studying the subject, and this creates a special emotional perception of the educational material. All of the above justifies the feasibility of their practical application in the education system; reflects their impact on teaching methods and the learning process; examples of educational technologies and tools are given. Particular attention is paid to innovative teaching methods, including using Skype, blogs, Internet sites, electronic dictionaries, providing new opportunities for effective language learning, making this process more informative and interesting. The relevance of this problem lies in the fact that innovative forms of learning are characterized by a high communicative ability and the active inclusion of students in educational activities, activate the potential of knowledge and skills of speaking and listening skills, and effectively develop communicative competence skills in younger students. This helps to adapt to modern social conditions, as society needs people who are quickly oriented in the modern world, independent and initiative, who achieve success in their activities. At the heart of any innovation is creativity. Creative activity involves the development of the emotional and intellectual spheres of personality. This is one of the main tasks of the modern educational process. Learning activities at school require the use of specific technologies that provide a solution to this problem. These are innovative forms of training: role-playing, project method, dramatization, elements of the Language Portfolio technology, ICT, techniques of critical thinking technology. Innovative activity is one of the most accessible and effective forms of developing communicative competence skills among younger students, creating conditions for the socialization of the individual and the development of its independence, creativity and activity. An important component is the creation of comfortable psychological conditions in which the student feels his success, intellectual solvency. It is for an elementary school in which the child's education coincides with the period of his intensive personal development, the use of the project method, role-playing games, and dramatization is especially important. Technology that stimulates the interests of primary schoolchildren and develops a desire to learn is associated with the implementation of various kinds of projects. Using this technology allows you to provide all possible forms of work in the classroom: individual, group, collective, which stimulate the independence and creativity of children.

Using the elements of the "Language Portfolio" technology in the lessons allows you to increase students' motivation in learning English, which, as a rule, leads to increased learning outcomes; provides a personality-oriented nature of learning, conditions for the manifestation of creativity and creative self-realization primary schoolchildren in the educational environment. This is facilitated by the work of children with the third section - "My piggy bank" (Dossier) and their participation in exhibitions.

The techniques of critical thinking technology in English lessons teach schoolchildren how to organize their activities, the ability to think, competent and meaningful reading, the ability to collaborate, etc.

Design technology. In elementary school, it is possible to use both mini - projects designed for one lesson or part of it, and large projects that require a long time to complete them. Projects can be individual (for example, a collage or an album "Let me introduce myself - this is me", "My family tree") and group ("We are about ourselves", "Our hometown"). In the lessons in the second and fourth grades, the following design tasks were used:

"We question each other." The children were offered various questionnaire options:

- a) "Interview your friends, and then tell who eats (drinks) what at breakfast (lunch, dinner).

"We make a collage." Each child at home works independently, using photographs, drawings, creating 'slide presentations'; I offer children topics and a rough plan:

- a) "I am about myself" (my name, the names of my parents, sisters, brothers; address; my age; birthday; my appearance; my interests);
- b) "My hometown" (name; geographical location; monuments; my favorite places);

The teacher, a “consultant,” asks questions in English: “What are you doing?”, “What is this?”, “What color?”, Gives tips: “Cut carefully”, comments on the actions of children: “Well done, you do everything right” etc.

In a lesson on the topic “Traveling to London”, a situation was suggested: students won a ticket to London, they want to learn more about the sights of the capital. Some students will live in an English family. They fly to London by plane. The type of project is mixed, because there are signs of research, creative and role-playing projects. Work on the project was carried out in several stages. In the first lesson, the students were offered a situation and a discussion was organized on the main content of the future project. As a result of the discussion, problems were selected, areas of work were identified, a project plan was drawn up. Working materials were prepared for the project: a mock-up of a map of London, photographs and a достопримечательностей slide presentation of London sights, a draft guide to London Sights, mock-ups of shop windows and cafes, and the necessary props. At the initial stage of the lesson, a repetition of a PO and a cliché of etiquette character was organized (“At the store”, “At the cafe”, “Asking the way”, etc.).

At the end of the lesson, the results were summarized:

What have students learned linguistically? (They know how to buy something in a store, make an order in a cafe, ask for directions.) How has their communication activity changed? (They can, interacting with each other, collectively politely thank, ask, offer, refuse, etc.) What is the contribution of the project to the overall development of the student? (He can play a role, speak expressively and emotionally.) What universal actions have children mastered? (They can independently search for the necessary information.)

Conclusion:

Thus, we can conclude that the use of modern technology in the lessons of a foreign (English) language is the most effective means of developing cognitive motivation of students, which involves the active cooperation of the teacher and student and students with each other. It is necessary to note the positive emotional mood of students towards each other, to the lesson as a whole, as well as their increased activity, desire to broaden their horizons, acquire new knowledge on the topic being studied, increase the quality of knowledge on the subject, as well as participation in various Olympiads and competitions. The given results confirm the effectiveness of using modern methods and techniques in teaching English. To carry out the tasks facing teachers of foreign languages, it is necessary to constantly work on self-education. A wide selection of methodological literature, visual aids, wide possibilities of a computer, Internet resources provide an opportunity for creative work. I believe that it is necessary to widely use information and communication technologies in the educational and educational processes in order to:

- be a technically competent specialist;
- keep abreast of all events in education;
- make the learning process more visual, accessible, exciting, informative;
- intensify the creative activities of students.

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